

Effect of Perchloric acid on Growth and Physical characteristics of Potassium Dihydrogen Phosphate Nonlinear Optical Crystals

S.Akilandeswari ^a and L.Jothi ^{b*}

**^{a, b}Department of Physics, Namakkal Kavignar Ramalingam Government Arts College for Women,
Namakkal - 637001, Tamilnadu, India**

*** Corresponding author:**

E-mail: jothilakshmanan@gmail.com

TEL: 9442921205

Abstract

Potassium dihydrogen phosphate is well known nonlinear optical material for various optoelectronics applications. Potassium dihydrogen phosphate continues to be interesting materials both academically and industrially. The overwhelming success of molecular engineering in controlling nonlinear optical properties in last decade has prompted better initiative in crystal engineering. In the present study single crystals of pure and perchloric acid doped potassium dihydrogen phosphate in different ratios has been synthesized by slow evaporation solution growth technique. The synthesized products are characterized by X-ray diffraction, Fourier Transform Infrared, UV-VIS-NIR, thermal analysis and micro hardness studies. The crystalline property and cell parameters of the grown crystals are studied by X-ray diffraction analysis. The shifting in frequency assignment of different functional group of Potassium dihydrogen phosphate due to addition of perchloric acid is analyzed by Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy. Transmission of light radiation from the grown material is identified from UV-VIS-NIR studies. Melting point of the grown crystal is obtained using melting point apparatus. Micro hardness test carried out at room temperature revealed that the grown materials belong to soft category.

Keywords : Crystal from solution, Characterization, X-ray diffraction, Micro hardness.

References :

1. H.V. Alexandru, S. Antoh , J. Cryst. Growth, 258 (2003) 149.
2. D. Xu, D.Xue, J. Cryst.Growth, 310(2008) 1385-1390.